

ANALYSIS OF KINK BAND FORMATION
UNDER COMPRESSION

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ABSTRACT

The kink band formation in unidirectional composites under compression is analyzed in the present paper. The kinematics of kink band formation is described in terms of a deformation tensor. Equilibrium conditions are then applied to relate the compression load to the deformation of fibers. Since the in situ shear behavior of the matrix resin is not known, an analysis-experiment correlation is used to find the shear failure strain in the kink band. The present analysis thus elucidates the mechanisms and identifies the controlling parameters, of compression failure.

INTRODUCTION

Kinking is a compression failure mode that appears to be associated with material anisotropy. It is found in single crystals of Cd [1], oriented rods of polyethylene [2], oriented rods of Nylon [3], anisotropic rocks [4], paperboards [5], and wood [6]. In composites also, fiber kinking is known to accompany compression failure. Fibers such as glass and graphite are believed to kink as a result of localized microbuckling. Highly anisotropic fibers, however, may fail first and kink subsequently. Examples include aramid fibers and high-modulus graphite fibers. These

fibers fail as a result of kinking of fibrils and consequently have low compression strengths.

A kink band is schematically shown in Fig. 1. In a two-dimensional setting, the band is characterized by the kink orientation angle α , the kink band angle β , and the kink length δ .

Several investigators have addressed the kink band formation in composites. Berg and Salama [7] suggested that kinking was caused by microbuckling of fibers. The obliquity of kink bands was attributed to the minimization of strain energy within the bands [8-10]. In particular, the kink band angle was predicted to be one-half the kink orientation angle. The kink orientation angle was in turn determined by minimizing the plastic work done on the matrix during fiber rotation [10].

Fig. 1. A schematic kink band geometry

Another method of predicting the kink band angle was proposed in [11]. It is based on the assumption of inextensible deformation of the composite under compression. The elastic fiber rotation due to an imperfection at an edge was determined and the locus of maximum fiber rotation was equated to the kink band angle. Furthermore, the kink length was obtained from the assumption that the matrix within the kink band was perfectly plastic and that the fibers broke when their tensile failure strain was reached.

In the present paper we propose a unified analysis of kink band formation. Although our approach is similar to the one in [11], it is different in that all three parameters are determined in just one unified analysis. Since more fundamental material properties required in the analysis are not known, a semi-empirical approach is taken. That is, the in situ material properties will be determined from the observed values of the kink band parameters using the proposed equations.

ANALYSIS

Figure 1 shows a kink band observed after failure. The deformation within the band is described by a deformation tensor $\underset{\sim}{F}$ given by

$$\underset{\sim}{F} = \begin{bmatrix} F_{11} & F_{12} & 0 \\ F_{21} & F_{22} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} . \quad (1)$$

The deformation tensor F must satisfy the conditions that the kink band boundary does not deform and that the deformation of fiber segments is a simple rotation through angle α . Consequently, the components F_{ij} are related to the angles by

$$\begin{aligned} F_{11} &= \cos \alpha , & F_{12} &= (\cos \alpha - 1) \tan \beta , \\ F_{21} &= \sin \alpha , & F_{22} &= 1 + \sin \alpha \tan \beta . \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Consider two unit vectors $\underset{\sim}{v}$ and $\underset{\sim}{w}$ that, before kinking, are given by

$$\underset{\sim}{v} = \underset{\sim}{i} , \quad \underset{\sim}{w} = \underset{\sim}{j} . \quad (3)$$

After kinking, these two vectors deform to

$$\underset{\sim}{Fv} = F_{11}\underset{\sim}{i} + F_{21}\underset{\sim}{j} , \quad \underset{\sim}{Fw} = F_{12}\underset{\sim}{i} + F_{22}\underset{\sim}{j} . \quad (4)$$

The resulting change ΔA in the area defined by $\underset{\sim}{v}$ and $\underset{\sim}{w}$ becomes

$$\Delta A = [\cos (\alpha - \beta)] / \cos \beta - 1 \quad (5)$$

Also, the shear strain γ is given by

$$\gamma = \sin \alpha + (1 - \cos \alpha) \tan \beta . \quad (6)$$

The condition that there be no volumetric change within the kink band requires that $\alpha = 2\beta$ [8-10]. Although there are some experimental data indicating the validity of no volume change, it should be noted that the

kink orientation α depends on the amount of deformation allowed after kinking. If the load is permitted to increase even after kinking failure, α will certainly increase although β does not change any more. Therefore, α must be taken as the kink orientation just before final collapse if it is to be related to β . With this new interpretation for α , it will be shown later that the assumption of no volume change does not hold true.

Micrographic evidences suggest that kink bands form in three steps: elastic kinking, plastic kinking, and then final collapse as a result of fiber failure at the kink boundaries. The elastic kinking is initiated at a defect such as void, fiber curvature, and poor bonding. In the plastic kinking stage, the matrix within the kink band yields in shear. Since the plastic kinking is believed to determine the kink band geometry, it will be analyzed in detail in the following.

Figure 2 shows a kinked fiber and the forces acting on it. Since

Fig. 2. A kinked fiber: (a) before collapse; (b) free body diagram for an infinitesimal element

fibers kink in phase with one another, one may assume $p = q = 0$. Further, the assumption of a constant axial force P is used to reduce the equilibrium conditions for the transverse forces and bending moments to the following equation for the slope w of the deflected fiber axis [12]:

$$d^2w/ds^2 + Pw/(E_f I_f) = A_f \tau_y / (E_f I_f) \tag{7}$$

Here s is the distance along the fiber axis; E_f , I_f , A_f are the modulus, moment of inertia, and cross-sectional area, respectively, of the fiber; and τ_y is the yield stress in shear.

The appropriate boundary conditions are

$$d\omega/ds = 0 \text{ at } s = 0; \quad \omega = d\omega/ds = 0 \text{ at } s \geq s_0. \quad (8)$$

The solution to Eq. (7) is thus

$$\omega = (A_f \tau_y / P) \{1 + \cos [P / (E_f I_f)]^{1/2} s\}, \quad (9)$$

$$s_0 = \pi (E_f I_f / P)^{1/2}. \quad (10)$$

The fiber will break where the curvature is maximum. The maximum fiber curvature is obtained from Eq. (9) as

$$(d\omega/ds)_{\max} = (d\omega/ds)_{s=s_0} = 4 \tau_y d_f / (\sigma_f E_f)^{1/2} \quad (11)$$

where d_f is the fiber diameter, and

$$s_m = s_0/2, \quad P = A_f \sigma_f \quad (12)$$

The resulting maximum strains in the fiber are finally given by

$$\epsilon^{(+)} = 2\tau_y / (\sigma_f E_f)^{1/2} - \sigma_f / E_f : \quad \text{tensile} \quad (13)$$

$$\epsilon^{(-)} = 2\tau_y / (\sigma_f E_f)^{1/2} + \sigma_f / E_f : \quad \text{compressive} \quad (14)$$

The fiber failure will be initiated on the tension side if Eq. (13) exceeds the tensile failure strain, or on the compression side if Eq. (14) exceeds the compressive failure strain. The applied fiber stress is then obtained from Eq. (13) or (14) depending on the failure mode.

The kink orientation is equal to the maximum slope at the time of fiber failure, and therefore is given by

$$\alpha = 2 \tau_y / \sigma_f \quad (15)$$

The kink length δ is equal to twice s_m ,

$$\delta = (\pi d_f / 4) (E_f / \sigma_f)^{1/2} \quad (16)$$

In the present analysis, the matrix was assumed to be perfectly plastic, and hence the shear strain at the time of collapse is indeterminate. Consequently, the kink band angle cannot be determined from Eq. (6) although α is known. An alternate is to use the assumption of no volume change or minimum strain energy in the kink band. In either case, the kink band angle turns out to be one-half the kink orientation as discussed earlier [8-10].

The foregoing equations predict all pertinent parameters for a kink band. The applied fiber stress at failure is determined from Eq. (13) or (14). It can then be used to predict the compression strength of the composite. The kink orientation and the kink length are given by Eqs. (15) and (16), respectively. Finally, the kink band angle is taken as one-half the kink orientation angle.

EXPERIMENTAL CORRELATION

Three types of unidirectional composites were tested to observe the kink band formation. They were graphite/epoxy, Kevlar/epoxy, and S glass/epoxy. The first two composites were tested at room temperature while the last was tested at 100°C. Details of the test results are given in [12].

On the average, the graphite/epoxy composite showed the smallest kink band angle (19°) and the smallest kink lengths (0.07 to 0.2 mm). The Kevlar/epoxy composite showed the largest kink band angle (39°) and the next smallest kink length (0.45 mm). The next largest kink band angle (32°) and the largest kink length (1.2 mm) were observed in the S glass/epoxy composite.

Table 1 lists both input properties and the predictions based on the equations of the preceding section. Fiber stresses at failure were obtained by dividing the compression strengths of respective composites by their fiber volume fractions.

TABLE 1

Predicted values of bending strains, kink orientation angle, kink length, and shear strain at failure

	Graphite/Epoxy	Kevlar/Epoxy	S Glass/Epoxy
Input Properties			
Fiber Volume Fraction V_f	0.60	0.65	0.65
Compression Strength (MPa)	1300	228	670
Fiber Stress (MPa)	2166	351	1030
Fiber Modulus (GPa)	230	130	85
Shear Yield Stress (MPa)	68	27	39
Kink Band Angle (Deg.)	19	39	32
Predicted Values			
Tensile Bending Strain (%)	-0.33	0.53	-0.38
Compressive Bending Strain (%)	1.55	1.07	2.04
Kink Orientation Angle (Deg.)	3.6	8.8	4.3
Kink Length/Fiber Diameter	8.0	24.5	7.1
Shear Strain at Failure (%)	6.2	14.3	7.3

The calculated bending strains on the tension side are either very small or negative. However, the bending strains on the compression side seem reasonable. Thus, fiber failure is proven to be initiated on the compression side at points of maximum fiber curvature. The compressive bending strain for the Kevlar fiber is larger than expected. One reason may be that the Kevlar fiber continued to bend beyond the elastic limit when kink bands were formed.

The predicted kink lengths for the graphite and Kevlar composites agree fairly well with the experimental values discussed earlier. The prediction is too low for the S glass composite. The exact reason for such a discrepancy is not clear at present. The large failure strain of S glass fiber might have allowed the kink band to grow even after failure.

The predicted kink orientation angles are considerably smaller than those experimentally observed after failure. Again, the predictions are at the onset of fiber failure. Once failure has occurred, the kink orientation angle can increase rapidly if the load is not immediately removed.

Since the observed kink band angles were much larger than one-half the corresponding kink orientation angles, shear strains at failure were calculated instead using Eq. (6). The results show that the kink bands undergo a significant amount of shear deformation. The local shear deformation at failure is the greatest in the Kevlar/epoxy. Both the graphite/epoxy and S glass/epoxy composites show almost the same amount of shear deformation.

SUMMARY

The kink band formation in unidirectional composites has been analyzed under the assumption that the matrix is perfectly plastic. Kink bands were assumed to be the result of in-phase bending failure of fibers. Equilibrium conditions were used to determine the fiber deformation. A deformation tensor was used to describe the deformation within the kink band.

Since not all the basic material parameters required in the analysis were available, they instead were determined from the measured composite properties using the analysis. The analysis indicated a substantial amount of plastic shear deformation occurring within kink bands. Although all geometric details of kink bands could not be predicted, the analysis is helpful in identifying pertinent material and structural parameters.

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